

An Assessment of the Effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation Methods on the Performance of County Government Projects in the Lake Region Economic Bloc of Nyanza, Kenya

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Abstract: In Kenya, the newly promulgated constitution of 2010 (CoK, 2010), provides the basis of monitoring and evaluation as an important tool for operationalizing National and County Government projects to ensure projects success, integrity, transparency and accountability. The county governments are responsible for delivering basic services in collaboration with other agencies and partners to enhance quality of life; however, the county government projects has been marred by lack of integrity, transparency, accountability and litany of other monitoring and evaluation weakness which has undermined the impacts and success of projects including Regional Economic Blocs. Lake Region Economic Bloc (LREB) which comprised of fourteen counties bordering Lake Victoria Basin is not spared either. The study was conducted in six LREB Counties namely, Migori, Homabay, Kisumu, Siaya, Kakamega and Vihiga chosen in a random manner. This study specifically assessed the effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation methods on the Performance of County Governments Projects. The study was guided by the theory of change. The research was carried out using descriptive survey design which entails both qualitative and quantitative data collection procedures. The researcher used stratified random sampling techniques to draw a sample from the study population. The qualitative method focused on group discussion and in-depth interviews. The quantitative techniques employed questionnaires to 398 purposively selected subjects from the county projects. Data collection was from two main sources; primary and secondary. Secondary sources included relevant county documents, constitution, legislations, policy documents and reports among others. The Study employed questionnaires, Focus group discussion and Interview guide as its primary data collection method. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 18.0 was used for analysis. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics techniques and presented in tables and figures. The study findings indicated that M&E methods, indicated by the coefficient of effectiveness (R²) which is also evidenced by F change 109.403 > p-values (0.05). This implies that this variable is significant (since the p values < 0.05) and therefore should be considered as part of effectiveness of M&E systems on the performance of County Governments projects. The study concludes that there are no effective and adequate projects monitoring and evaluation methods in place for County Government Projects, which can facilitate the achievement of desired projects performance and outcomes. The study recommends that the County Government should develop a clear M&E methods for each project with clear data collection, analysis, reporting and implementation methods. This Study recommends further research to be conducted in the other Regional County Economic Blocs.

Key Words: M&E methods, Transparency, Accountability, Integrity, success, projects performance

I. Introduction

Monitoring and evaluation is an ongoing function that employs the systematic collection of data related to specified indicators in projects or programs. Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) is described as a process that assists project managers in improving performance and achieving results. The goal of M&E is to improve current and future management of outputs, outcomes and impact (UNDP, 2008). Williams (2000) asserts that, monitoring provides management and the main stakeholders of a development intervention with indications of the extent of progress and achievement of expected results and progress with respect to the use of allocated funds. Monitoring is the continuous collection of data on specified indicators to assess for a development intervention (project, programme or policy) its

implementation in relation to activity schedules and expenditure of allocated funds, and its progress and achievements in relation to its objectives. Monitoring provides essential inputs for evaluation and therefore constitutes part of the overall evaluation procedure. Evaluation is an organized and objective assessment of an ongoing or concluded policy, program/project, its design, execution and results. The aim is to provide timely assessments of the relevance, efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability of interventions and overall progress against original objectives. According to Willard (2008), monitoring and evaluation is a process that helps program implementers make informed decisions regarding program operations, service delivery and project effectiveness, using objective evidence.

Developed countries like the USA, China and Russia have resorted to decentralization of resources. Decentralization refers to “the transfer of political power, decision making capacity and resources from central to sub-national levels of government (Zaltsman, 2006). This has led to resuscitation of old institutions that seemed to offer opportunities for decentralization and devolution. Since 1990s decentralization and devolution has been linked to collective empowerment and democracy due to failure of institutional reforms to reduce poverty (Zaltsman, 2006). Democratic decentralization and devolution is more focused on democracy pluralism and human rights (Cook 2006, United Nations Capital Development Fund, 2004). Effective monitoring and evaluation is critical to the successful implementation and achievement of results for any project. Monitoring and Evaluation is understood to be part of programme managing cycle and as the best way of measuring progress, detecting problems, correcting them, improving performance and learning levels. Institutionalization of M&E has meant creation of M&E structures, systems and process with policy, legal and institutional arrangements to produce monitoring information and evaluation findings have been judged valuably by key stakeholders (Woodhill, 2006). Institutionalized M&E has served as an integral part of the development policy/programme cycle in improving the performance accountability to provide effective feedback which has improved planning, budgeting and policy making that has achieved development effectiveness.

In Canada, M&E system has invested heavily in both evaluation and performance monitoring as key tools to support accountability and results-based management. Furthermore, the current state of the M & E structure has evolved over time, as the central designers have recognized that the development and implementation of M & E is long term and iterative, therefore putting emphasis on the structure of implementation as an important mechanism in itself in developing an evaluation culture or “results culture” in an organization and across the entire system (Mulwa and Ngulu, 2007). According to ADB, (2009), since the early 1990s, monitoring and evaluation (M&E) has seen a steep climb within Sub-Saharan Africa, in terms of practice, profession and academic study. As a field of practice, specialized departments housing the practitioners now exist and the demand for evaluation of policies, projects, program and interventions remains on the increase. Legal and institutional frameworks for the practices of M&E are still weak in Africa (UNEG, 2017). As a profession, over 30 national evaluation associations under the umbrella body, the African Evaluation Association (AFREA) are in existence. As an academic field of study several institutions now offer programmes in M&E; notwithstanding the focus and locus dilemma regarding the discipline. Scholarship regarding the state of the field is thus of utmost importance to coherently describe the ‘ups and downs’ of the new field which has become a ‘grown up child’ having jumped the infancy stage (Basheka & Byamugisha, 2015)

In Africa, M&E systems operate in complex terrain. To some extent they are hostages to other forces in government and those in authority, however given a results driven reform agenda, incentives can be put in place for the evidence generated to support developments in delivering results and budgeting (UNICEF, 2008). Monitoring and evaluation are consistently designed to support valued change in people’s lives, particularly the underprivileged (Pollitt, 2009). In effect, the tools of governance are aligned to citizenry, not internal bureaucratic desires. The significance of results placement for government is extensively deliberated, and finds manifestation in public management and development literature (Baker, 2000; Bamberger, 2009; OECD, 2005).

In Ghana, after several years of implementing the National M&E System, significant progress has been made (Kessides, 1993). However, challenges include severe financial constraints; institutional, operational and technical capacity constraints; fragmented and uncoordinated information, particularly at the sector level. To address these challenges the Clear report argues that the current institutional arrangements will have to be reinforced with adequate capacity, clear structures, systems and process to support and sustain effective monitoring and evaluation, and existing M & E mechanisms must be strengthened, harmonized and effectively coordinated (Koffi, 2002).

In Kenya, Monitoring and Evaluation forms part of a result culture in the public service that is meant to provide value and service for all Kenyans. In the planning and implementation of development efforts, monitoring and evaluation is to ensure that intended targets are reached, remedies are taken when projects are off-track, and the lessons learned are used to promote efficiency and effectiveness (GoK, 2015). Furthermore, the constitution of 2010 provides the framework and basis for M&E as an important part of operationalizing government activities both at the national government and County Government levels to ensure that transparency, integrity and accountability principles are embraced in resources allocation, usage and management at national and devolved levels of Government. In addition,

the scope of M&E is derived from the articles and provisions related to planning under articles 10, 56, 174, 195, 225 and 227 of the Constitution of Kenya, 2010. It proposes a robust M&E process as essential for efficient and effective implementation of MTP 2013-2017, County Integrated Development Plans (CIDP), and Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDA) Strategic Plans. The Act and Policies related to M&E, supports the implementation of a computerized National Integrated Monitoring and Evaluation System (NIMES) from the national, county and the local levels of government agencies, it established Ministerial M&E committee and County M&E committees chaired by Principal Secretaries and County Governors respectively MTP-2013-17, (GoK, 2015).

The legal mechanism spelt out in the 2010 Constitution has necessitated the development of M&E systems for the County Governments in Kenya. The constitution further demands adherence to transparency in conducting and management of public development projects and to the principle of good governance. The national and County Governments are therefore united in the recognition that performance monitoring and evaluation is a pivotal development process in the country. Both the national and County Governments are therefore increasing their focus on results and how they can better be measured (GoK, 2015). The Act and Policies related to M&E ensures that all Ministries and County Governments establish M&E units with specific budgets employ qualified M&E officers and acquire appropriate equipment for effective implementation of NIMES (GoK, 2012). It calls for capacity building and training on M&E both at national and local level throughout the MTP period to ensure effective implementation of NIMES. The stakeholders and the public are to access data on implementation of programs and projects at county levels through various channels, structures and forums. In spite of the foregoing, the influence of M&E systems, methods and structures on completion and success of the projects is not accorded significance in many County Government projects. In order for a county to achieve any meaningful economic growth and development, there is need therefore for sound economic policies. These policies should be the guide to program and projects on which development is pegged. Mackay (2007) and UNICEF (2009) pointed out that M&E has emerged as a Key economic policy development and performance management tool which is aimed at reducing economic and project risks and uncertainties. Both argue that economic policy makers need the information generated from M&E to improve their economic performance while tax payers, donors and stakeholders need M&E results to ensure accountability of resources while at the same time improving the overall effectiveness of their policies (Kelly and Mangongo, 2015).

The major phase in the evolution of M&E in Kenya was the introduction of the Kenya Vision 2030 in 2008, which replaced the Economic recovery Strategy (ERS) as the country's development blueprint. Vision 2030 became the principle driver of development in Kenya and therefore the basis for National Integrated Monitoring and Evaluation System (NIMES). When in 2008, Kenya Vision 2030 as the national developmental policy replaced ERS; NIMES was re-oriented to M&E of the implementation of the Vision 2030 (GoK, 2012). The M&E responsibility was at this time, however, divided between Monitoring and Evaluation Directorate (MED) and a new tailor made body, within the then, Ministry of Planning responsible for flagship programs and projects in Kenya Vision 2030. The Kenya Vision 2030 Board and its Secretariat were created for that purpose. NIMES was designed to have a three tier institutional relationship for generating M&E information. At the national level is MED, that provides leadership and coordinates the system by ensuring that two vital sources of M&E information, namely Annual Progress Reports (APRs) on the Medium Term Plan (MTP) of Vision 2030 and Annual Public Expenditure Review (PER) are ably and timely produced (GoK, 2012). At ministerial level are the Central Project Planning and Monitoring Units (CPPMUs). The CPPMUs produce Ministerial Annual Monitoring and Evaluation Reports (MAMERs), and Ministerial Public Expenditure Reviews (MPERs) which are synthesized into the APR and PER respectively. At sub-national level, the District Development Officers, supervised by the Provincial Directors of Planning, were meant to produce the District Annual Monitoring and Evaluation Reports, (GoK, 2012).

Kenya government budget process takes into account the PER which is complemented by the work that goes into preparation of Ministerial Annual Monitoring and Evaluation Reports that subsequently becomes Annual Progress Reports on the implementation of Vision 2030 from the NIMES system (GoK, 2012). As one of the flagship projects of Kenya's M&E information, the Public Expenditure Review is an analysis, which covers vital factors as macroeconomic performance, spending trends, and implications for each of Kenya's socioeconomic and governance sectors. More recently the PER has begun to benchmark Kenya's economic management against selected peer countries that the country aspires to emulate. Despite the numerous efforts that have been made under NIMES and through the PER and APR, Kenya's M&E system still faces challenges (GoK, 2012). Kenya's Constitution has fundamentally changed central and devolved governance structures and provides an opportunity for strengthening her M&E system structures and methodology. By underscoring timely and accurate information sharing to support policymaking, the Constitution is calling for a stronger nation-wide and counties M&E systems and structures. This provides the greatest strength and opportunity for a county's M&E system in Kenya in support of the realization of the Kenya Vision 2030 blue print which is being implemented through successive five-year Medium Term Plans and is aimed at enabling the Kenyan

nation to achieve the long-term development goals. Kenya is now in the second medium term plan cycle (2013-2017). It's also noted that the Government of Kenya works in two levels, the National Government and the County Government respectively. For the National Government to achieve its big four Agenda, she relies heavily on the achievements of County Government projects.

In 2007, the Government recognized the importance of M&E in promoting accountability and enhancing good governance, as a result the government through Ministry of Planning and National Development established a Monitoring and Evaluation Unit (MEU) to coordinate the implementation of NIMES. MEU later on became the Monitoring and Evaluation Department (MED). The Government of Kenya has undertaken development planning since independence. The ministry responsible for planning has been in existence even in the period prior to 2010 promulgated constitution of Kenya. Since then it has existed as a separate entity or a part of a wider Ministerial docket. The planning function has over the years been executed with complains of non-implementation of highly ambitious plans and projects. Execution of development projects has remained elusive over years partly because of weak or non-existent Monitoring and Evaluation, policy and Systems. Project supported by Development partners have normally had a good policy, systems and as such their performance has been regularly assessed, monitored and evaluated. Comprehensive monitoring and evaluation plans are included in their design and at times implemented through M&E units specifically established for each project or this purpose (Kelly and Mangongo, 2004).

1.1. County Governments Monitoring and Evaluation Framework in Kenya

County Governments have two levels of Project Monitoring and Evaluation these levels were created to support in delivering the vision 2030 and were pegged to their deliverables towards county specific target (GoK,2015). At county level, the Governors, as county chief executives is expected to be the key champion for their respective counties move to focus on results. Among the responsibilities and functions provided for the County governor in the Constitution is the submission of annual report on the implementation of county policies and development project plans to the county assembly, promotion of competitiveness of the county and accountability in the management and use of county resources. The Governor is to produce M&E reports as a permanent feature. The County M&E policy spelt a need for counties to establish the capacity to successfully construct the M&E indicators and their baseline and the skills and capacity to utilize the M&E information and data collected. In the organizational structure, counties were also to establish and identify who regularly collects and analyses result based M&E information to assess the County Government's performance (Gok,2014).

According to Ministry of Devolution and Planning, (M & E Framework, 2015), the County institutional M&E structure at county level is to be inclusive and accommodative in order to provide coverage and voice of all categories of institutions and agencies which co-exist at the county level. This include the county administration at the county, sub-county and lower levels, constituencies, local private sector organizations, civil society organizations (CSOs) and other non-state actors. As stipulated in the M&E policy framework, every county is further required to establish a Monitoring and Evaluation Committee known as the County Monitoring and Evaluation Committee (CoMEC).

The various categories of institutions, agencies and departments at the county to form M&E units and be represented at the CoMEC. This committee is to do among other things produce County Annual Monitoring and Evaluation Reports(CAMERs), coordinate the county M&E systems among other stipulated functions (GoK,2015).The Sub-county M&E committees (Sub-CoMEC) follows up on the development progress at their level and even at the ward level, carry out routine monitoring and evaluation, collect and collate data, and prepare progress reports that is submitted to the CoMEC on quarterly basis through Sub-County Development Committee (Sub-CoDC). Within the M&E structure of the County Governments, there is County Stakeholders Forum (CSF) convened by the governor's office to review monitoring and evaluation reports and provide feedback before publication with specific attention to County Annual Monitoring and Evaluation Report (CAMERs) (GoK,2015). The County M&E Unit is responsible for coordination and implementation of M&E functions at the county level.

Figure 1: A refined linkages between Central and County Government Project Plans in Kenya
Source: GoK, 2015.

1.2 Regional Economic Blocs (REBs) in Kenya

Regional Economic blocs are groups of counties in specific regions that has joined up together to manage and promote trade activities among themselves. Regional *blocs* lead to trade and trade creation between members, since they are treated favorably in comparison to non-members. They contribute or pool resources to address some common challenges facing them. In Kenya, these Economic Blocs has been formed by the county governors based on regional economic activities and shared resources in order to drive growth. Although reading of the Constitution reveals that there is still no relevant statutes such as the County Governments Act, the Inter-Governmental Relations Act and Public Finance Management Act shows that there is no legislation or policy framework to guide and regulate these Regional Economic Blocs (REBs), however reports indicate that attempts are being made by governors through county assemblies to anchor the regional blocs in the law.

In Kenya, according to Council of Governors (CoG), there are six (6) Regional Economic Blocs (REBs) formed by County Governments or devolved units brought together by common interests such as marketing, agricultural produce and tourism sites, as well as trade and investment that cut across their regions. They are Lake Region Economic Bloc (LREB) comprising of 14 counties, North Rift Economic Bloc (NREB) made up of 7 Counties, Frontier Counties Development Council (FCDC) formed by 7 Counties, JumuiyaKauntizaPwani has 6 Counties, Central Economic Bloc (CEB) comprising 10 Counties and South Eastern Kenya Economic Bloc (SEKEB) which is made up of 3 counties respectively. The 47 County Governments which has formed different Regional Economic Blocs are allocated more than Kshs 302 billion in 2015/16 and Kshs 334.7 billion in 2016/17 financial year for their recurrent and development expenditure of which not less than 30% of their expenditures should go to development projects according to CRA and County Government Act of 2015.

The Lake Region Economic Bloc (LREB) is made up of 14 counties surrounding Lake Victoria Basin. The Fourteen (14) Counties forming Lake Region Economic Bloc (LREB) received budget allocation of approximately Kshs 92.6 billion in the financial year 2016/2017. This comprises of approximately Kshs 37 billion for development budget and the rest is for the re-current expenditures (KNBS,2017).

II. Literature Review

2. Monitoring and Evaluation Methods and Approaches

Monitoring and Evaluation Methods and approaches is an area of growing importance for the development community (Zaltsman, 2006). It allows those involved in development activities to learn from experience, to achieve better results

and to be more accountable. There is increased interest in M&E methods among the development communities due to a stronger focus on the results produced and the means to produce them through interventions.

M&E methods and processes allow those involved to assess the impact of a particular activity, to determine how it could be done better using different methods and approaches and to show what action is being taken by different stakeholders (Scriven,1967) . This should translate into a more effective and transparent way of working. There are different methods that can be employed by the projects.

2.1 Result Oriented Approach Method of Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation methods are based on assumptions and expectations of causality and linearity, If we do this in the project, then this will happen and this or that change will take place, to put it another way, the project can plan for change and then measure it (Tan, 2005). The strength of result oriented methods lies in strategy and planning. They force project managers and participants to consider carefully what they want their contribution to be and how they think they should act to achieve this (Scriven,1967). In other words, they support the development or explication of the intervention strategy.

By developing an intervention strategy the project managers and participants can assess what works and what doesn't work at specific times. If necessary, the strategy can be modified along the way. As well as that, the result-oriented methods can be useful in monitoring the progress of the projects, the so-called operational process. Result-oriented methods are powerful instruments but they have their limitations in (system) innovation processes (Hahn, &Sharrock, 2010). An example of a well-known intervention strategy in system innovation is the stimulation of unforeseen contacts in order to trigger surprising new insights and initiatives (UNDP, 2008. ADB, 2009). During the implementation of a result oriented M&E, project managers and the participants will want answers to a number of questions. In the short term, to what degree they are successful in stimulating unforeseen contacts/output.

The strength of result-oriented methods lies in asking these pointed questions, but they can often only provide part of the answer(WB,2002). Collective learning and innovation processes do not evolve in a linear way but are unpredictable. As a consequence, cause and effect relations are not easily traceable. Result-oriented methods do not address the value of collective learning and the development of a shared vision, mission and understanding of the project and/or its context (Scriven,1967).

Governments and international development agencies are increasingly being called upon to demonstrate results. Besides demands for greater accountability and transparency, stakeholders are also demanding greater efficiency and effectiveness of development actions. As a result, a number of development agencies are promoting a results-management framework as a strategic approach to be applied in all aspects of the project cycle. Results-based monitoring and evaluation places particular emphasis on outcomes and impact (Willard,2008). It emphasizes that it is not sufficient simply to determine that planned outputs have been delivered on time and on budget. The 'ends' are more important than the 'means' and it is necessary to determine, and show evidence that, planned outcomes and a worthwhile contribution to national goals are being achieved.

A results-based management approach should enhance public sector performance generally, and is particularly applicable for programme and policy interventions at sector level which adopt a flexible approach to implementation, and for which 'inputs activities' and 'outputs' may not be fully specified in advance (AMES,2012).

A results-based approach is particularly important if a project is 'process-oriented' and designed with an open-ended strategy, general directions being indicated but detailed work plans and resource provision not specified in advance (Ghazala, & Vijayendra,2011). This may also apply to many sector level interventions. Clearly, it may not be possible to initially develop a full logical framework analysis of inputs, activities and outputs for the purposes of planning, although if useful this can be developed as a management tool during implementation for project or programme components, once these are agreed by project partners and take shape on the ground (PMI,2004).

2.2 Performance Indicators Method of Monitoring and Evaluation

These measure inputs, processes, outputs, outcomes and impacts of development interventions (Willard,2008). They are also used for setting targets and measuring progress towards the project (PMI,2004). Performance indicators are measures that describe how well a program is achieving its objectives (Saunders, Evans and Joshi, 2005). Whereas a results statement identifies what project hopes to accomplish, indicators tell specifically what to measure to determine whether the objective has been achieved (Issel, 2009). They define how performance will be measured along a scale or dimension, without specifying a particular level of achievement.

Performance indicators are at the heart of a performance monitoring system they define the data to be collected to measure progress and enable actual results achieved over time to be compared with planned results (Blamey

& Mackenzie, 2007). They are indispensable management tool for making performance based decisions about program and project strategies and activities.

2.3 Theory-Based Evaluation Approach Method of Monitoring and Evaluation

Similar to the Log Frame approach method, this provides a deeper understanding of the workings of a complex intervention (Scriven, 1967). It helps planning and management by identifying critical success factors (CSF). Chen, (1990), states that a theory of change explains how an intervention is expected to produce its results. The theory typically starts out with a sequence of events and results (outputs, immediate outcomes, intermediate outcomes and ultimate outcomes) that are expected to occur owing to the intervention (Funnell, & Rogers, 2011). This is commonly referred to as the program logic or logic model (Weiss, 2000). However, the theory of change goes further by outlining the mechanisms of change, as well as the assumptions, risks and context that support or hinder the theory from being manifested as observed outcomes. (Blamey, & Mackenzie, 2007).

2.4 Constructivist Approach Method of Monitoring and Evaluation

The constructivist M&E approach method assumes that people are the motor behind the development of novelties and societal change processes. They achieve this through interaction and negotiation (Guba and Lincoln, 1989). Mutual understanding and exchange of experiences support collective learning, improvement and change. Constructivist methods focus heavily on monitoring and evaluation of the progress of the collective learning process. They do not so much define the “what” question but highlight more how successful collective learning processes are initiated and prolonged the “how” question (Willard, 2008).

A central activity is sharing experiences from different perspectives by different people. An analysis of the most important issues is made on the basis of individual stories and together with the story-tellers, the group reflects on possible further steps. Related M&E methods are Learning Histories (Roggers, 2008), Networks Learning from Learning Histories, and Responsive Evaluation (Abma and Widdershoven, 2005). A method like Most Significant Change (Davies and Newcomer, 2006) also falls under this approach. The strength of constructivist methods is that they stimulate the exchange of perspectives. They ensure a good insight into how processes evolve. These insights are of value for the learning process itself and the relationships within the project or network.

2.5 Reflexive Approach Method of Monitoring and Evaluation

The most recent approach in M&E is reflexive. Reflexive method focuses on both a collective learning process (in groups of actors and in networks) as well as on the results in terms of learning and institutional change (Mayne, 2000). The reflexive approach has a constructivist basis but goes further. Project or network participants not only exchange their personal view points and motives but they also debate their presumptions and underlying values and norms and the institutional context in which they operate (Stetson, 2008). In this way, they can arrive at diverse agreements about possible joint actions.

Reflexive monitoring assumes that system innovation can only take place if the institutions (laws, regulations, culture, etc.) which have until now perpetuated the current (non-sustainable) practices change as well (Rossi, Peter, Mark and Howard, 2004). The leading question in reflexive monitoring is whether the activities in an innovation project stimulate precisely those learning processes that can lead to a change in current practices of interdependent parties. The strength of this approach is that it is based on thinking in terms of systems; current practices are questioned and the aim is to change a complete system (Hahn, & Sharrock, 2010).

The approach is promising for projects where the ambition is to contribute to system innovation. Because reflexive monitoring has not yet been implemented in practice very often, there are few people with knowledge and experience of it. It requires sincere commitment and intensive effort; self-monitoring is not or hardly possible. Related methods are the Interactive Learning Approach (Woodhill, 2006), Reflexive Process Monitoring and Reflexive Monitoring in Action. Reflexive Monitoring in Action (RMA) has mainly been conducted in the context of development projects (WB, 2002).

2.6 The logical Framework Method of Monitoring and Evaluation

The logical framework (LogFrame) helps to clarify objectives of any project, program, or policy. (Bakewell and Garbutt, 2005). It aids in the identification of the expected causal links the program logic in the following results chain: inputs, processes, expected outputs, outcomes, and impact. With growing emphasis on participatory approaches towards development, there has been recognition that monitoring and evaluation (M&E) should also be participatory. Conventionally, M&E has involved outside experts coming in to measure performance against pre-set indicators, using standardized procedures and tools. In contrast, participatory monitoring and evaluation (PM&E)

involves primary stakeholders as active participants and offers new ways of assessing and learning from change that are more inclusive, and reflects the perspectives and aspirations of those most directly affected (W B, 2010).

Bakewell and Garbutt (2005) suggest that use of logical framework leads to the identification of performance indicators at each stage in this chain, as well as risks which might impede the attainment of the objectives (Baker,2000). The LogFrame is also a vehicle for engaging partners in clarifying objectives and designing activities. During implementation the LogFrame serves as a useful tool to review progress and take corrective action

Figure 2: Logical framework Sequence model for effective monitoring and evaluation

Source: Turrall and Pasteur (2006)

2.7. Rapid appraisal Method of Monitoring and Evaluation

These are quick, cheap ways of providing decision-makers of the project with views and feedback from beneficiaries and stakeholders (Baker, 2000). They include interviewing, focus groups and field observation. Rapid Appraisal method of monitoring and evaluation is an approach that draws on multiple evaluation methods and techniques to quickly, yet systematically, collect data when time in the field is limited (Bergeron and Scherr, 1996). Rapid appraisal practices are also useful when there are budget constraints or limited availability of reliable secondary data. e.g. time and budget limitations may preclude the option of using representative sample surveys.

Rapid appraisal methods offer development workers a useful set of research and appraisal tools to obtain quickly information from local populations about their conditions and their needs (Abel and Stocking, 1979). The methods also enable local people and outsiders to plan together appropriate interventions and evaluate the impact of development interventions after these have been carried out. The method have distinct advantages because they generally involve low costs, are highly adaptable to different situations and tend to facilitate the establishment of rapport with local communities. They also favor analysis on the spot with local people, enabling verification of findings and enhancing the local relevance of results (Bamberger, and Mabry, 2006). Rapid Appraisal tends to raise expectations among the population about project activities. The method is further used to guide, inform the design and confirm findings from formal surveys. A combination of formal and rapid appraisal methods is the best way to ensure the quality of final results.

2.8. Participatory Method of Monitoring and Evaluation

The participatory approach allows project stakeholders to be actively involved in decision-making. They generate a sense of ownership of M&E results and recommendations, and build local capacity. With growing emphasis on participatory approaches towards development, there has been recognition that monitoring and evaluation (M&E) should also be participatory (Baker,2000).

Conventionally, M&E has involved outside experts coming in to measure performance against pre-set indicators, using standardized procedures and tools. In contrast, participatory monitoring and evaluation (PM&E) involves primary stakeholders as active participants and offers new ways of assessing and learning from change that are more inclusive, and reflects the perspectives and aspirations of those most directly affected (WB, 2010).

Participatory monitoring & evaluation (PM&E) is a process through which stakeholders at various levels engage in monitoring or evaluating a particular project, program or policy, share control over the content, the process and the results of the monitoring and evaluation (M&E) activity and engage in taking or identifying corrective actions, PM&E focuses on the active engagement of primary stakeholders (WB2010).

Participatory monitoring and evaluation is one of the approaches to ensure that the implementation of the different projects within the action plan or smaller individual projects leads to the expected outcomes. As with all other monitoring and evaluation elements, the process for PM&E has to be prepared prior to project implementation (Baker, 2000). The stakeholder groups typically involved in a participatory M&E activity includes the end users of project goods and services.

2.9 Cost-Benefit and Cost-Effectiveness Analysis Method

In cost benefit analysis, tools are used to assess whether the cost of an activity is justified by its impact (Brent, 2006). Cost-benefit measures inputs and outputs in monetary terms, whereas cost-effectiveness looks at outputs in non-monetary terms (Jimenez and Patrinos, 2008). Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a technique used to compare the total costs of programme/project with its benefits, using a common metric commonly monetary units. This enables the calculation of the net cost or benefit associated with the programme (Brent, 2006). As a technique, it is used most often at the start of a programme or project when different options or courses of action are being appraised and compared, as an option for choosing the best approach (Dennis and Denis, 1982). It can also be used, however, evaluate the overall impact of a programme in quantifiable and monetized terms. CBA adds up the total costs of a programme or activity and compares it against its total benefits. The technique assumes that a monetary value can be placed on all the costs and benefits of a programme, including tangible and intangible returns to other people and organizations in addition to those immediately impacted (Backer, 2000). As such, a major advantage of cost-benefit analysis lies in people to explicitly and systematically consider the various factors which should influence strategic choice.

2.10. Impact Evaluation Method

This is the systematic identification of the effects of an intervention on households, institutions and the environment. It can be used to gauge the effectiveness of the project activities in reaching the poor (Roche, 1999). Impact evaluation helps people answer key questions for evidence based policy focusing on what works, what doesn't, where, why and for how much. It has received increasing attention in policy making in recent years in the context of developing countries (Baker, 2000). It is an important component of evaluations tools and approaches and integral to global efforts to improve the effectiveness of service delivery and public spending more generally in improving living standards

11. Public Expenditure Tracking Surveys Method

Public Expenditure Tracking Surveys (PETS) are surveys that measure the amount of funds received at each point in the chain of public service delivery, from a nation's treasury to the classroom or health clinic where the funds are intended to be spent (Zaltsman, 2006). It traces the flow of public funds and assess whether resources reach the intended recipients. They can help diagnose service delivery problems and improve accountability (Gaitano, 2011). Jaszczolt, Potkanski and Stanislaw (2010), suggest that another important condition for success is to consider PETS as part of a broader strategy aimed at empowering communities to claim their entitlements. The experience illustrates that the release of tracking survey results significantly contribute to reducing leakage by promoting social ownership (Koffi, 2002). Even though reducing leakage over the long term requires a number of measures, such as sensitizing project staff, stakeholders and beneficiaries.

12. Theoretical Frameworks

The study was anchored on the theory of change, the theory suggests that a human society and organizations are like an organism and is made up of structures and methods called social institutions. These institutions are specially structured and have a methodology on how they perform different functions on behalf of the society or the organizations. The theory of change is verified by evidence on the chain of objectives and expected results.

12.1 Theory of Change

The approach involves change process for the intervention showing how the specific intervention is intended to work. It tends to address the traditional evaluation questions of whether and to what extent the project intervention has worked. The theory of change is developed on the basis of a range of stakeholders' views and information sources (Guba & Lincoln, 1989). In addressing the County Government monitoring and evaluation of projects performance issues using theory based method to monitoring and evaluation, the County Government identifies among other core issues, related to project objective, relevance, priority and performance (i.e. effectiveness and efficiency) that should be addressed in all project monitoring and evaluations undertaken in response to success. The theory of change in evaluation can be traced back to the late 1950s with Kirkpatrick's 'Four Levels of Learning Evaluation Model, input, processes, methods and products and the use of logical frameworks (logframes) or logical models which set out causal chains usually consisting of inputs, activities, outputs and outcomes and goals.

This theory suggests that a framework method is essential to guide monitoring and evaluation and explain how the project is supposed to work by laying out the components of the initiative and the order or the steps needed to achieve the desired results in order to increase the understanding of the project's goals and objectives, defines the relationships between factors key to implementation, and articulates the internal and external elements that could affect the project's success (Davis and Newcomer, 2006). The theory of change reflects the underlying process and pathways through which

the hoped for change (in knowledge, behavior, attitudes or practices, at the individual, institutional, community or other level) is expected to occur (Guba & Lincoln, 1989). Helene Clark and Andrea Anderson in Theories of Change and Logic Models: argues that theory of change adequately describes the actions, the desired change, and the underlying assumptions or strategy that is essential for monitoring and evaluating of project.

This is in congruence with Corlazzoli and White (2013), on theories of change in monitoring and evaluation method that using theories of change during the monitoring and evaluation stage of project implementation provides feedback on whether a project, programme or strategy is on track to accomplish the desired change and if the environment is evolving as anticipated in the project or programme design. The power of using theories of change is not only important in monitoring methods but also in evaluation methodology. Using theories of change during evaluation enables evaluators to ask hard questions about why certain changes are expected, the assumptions of how the change process unfolds, and which outcomes are being selected.

13 Conceptual Framework Model

Conceptual frameworks are diagrams that identify and illustrate relationships among relevant organizational, institutions, individual and other factors that may influence a project and the successful achievement of goals and objectives (Abma & Wilddershoven, 2005). They Help determine which factors will influence the project and outline how each of these factors underlying, structural, cultural, economic socio-political among others might relate to and affect the outcomes. They do not form the basis for monitoring and evaluation activities, but will help explain project results

14. Conceptual Framework model

.Source, (Author,2018)

15. Study Objective

The objective of the study was to assess Monitoring and Evaluation Methods on the performance of County Government projects in the Lake Region Economic Bloc counties of Nyanza, Kenya

16. Research Methodology and Design

16.1 Description of the Study Area

The Lake Region Economic Bloc Counties is one of the most densely populated regions of Kenya with over 10 million people which constitute about 25% of the population in Kenya. Their Economic Blueprint presents the socioeconomic aspirations of 14 counties in the Lake Basin Region and seeks to boldly secure and shape the region's destiny. Their Economic Blueprint was designed to guide development efforts by leveraging existing assets, addressing constraints and defining key steps that leaders and citizens of the region can take to transform the shared vision of prosperity into reality.

The Lake Region counties which form the Lake Region Economic Bloc (LREB) is made up of 14 counties bordering Lake Victoria, it acts as a one-stop shop for investors seeking opportunities in the region. It identifies seven strategic intervention areas (projects), namely: Agriculture, Tourism, Education, Health, ICT, Financial Services and Infrastructure. The fourteen (14) counties that constitute the Lake Region in the blueprint are Bungoma, Busia, Homa-Bay, Kakamega, Kisii, Kisumu, Migori, Nyamira, Bungoma, Kakamega, Kericho, Transzoia, Siaya and Vihiga. They not only have similar ecological zones and natural resources, they have analogous cultural histories that date back to historical migrations and trading routes. Thus a partnership between the counties is both essential and timely and creates a practical framework through which County Government efforts can be pooled to harness the abundant natural resources, build on existing strengths and address challenges. For each of the intervention areas, the blueprint has designated a flagship project to be implemented in the region. Their flagship projects are: an agricultural commodities exchange, a regional bank, specialist hospitals and educational centers of excellence in each county, creating a Lake region ring road and tourism circuit.

The Lake Region Economic Blueprint was initiated through a consultative process by the County Governments, including the public a part from individual counties' integrated development plans. Each of the counties identified one key pillar project for the economic bloc. The Lake Region Economic Blueprint is aligned with the national development plans of Vision 2030 and its Medium Term Plan II for 2013-2017, as well as the County Integrated Development Plans (CIDP) for each County Government.

16.2 Research Design

The study was conducted through a descriptive survey design, this described the situation and state of the affairs and conditions currently exist as regards monitoring and evaluation in the counties. Descriptive survey design is appropriate because it is not restricted only to the fact findings, but may often results in the formulation of important principles of knowledge and solutions to problems (Kerlinger, 2009). The design has been selected to facilitate rapid and cost effective collection of data and for its potential at enabling one understand the population as part of it. Furthermore, the researcher looked at the problem at hand thoroughly to define it, clarify it, and obtained pertinent information that may be useful to County Government's policy makers and oversight agencies. Several researchers have recommended it as the best for this kind of research (Orodho, 2004).

16.3 Target Population

Population is an identifiable total group or aggregation of elements/people that are of interest to a researcher and pertinent to the specified information problem Hair (2003). This includes defining the population from which our sample is drawn. According to Salkind (2008), population is the entire of some groups. This is also supported by Sekaran and Bougie (2010), population is defined as entire group of people the researcher wants to investigate.

The population of study consisted of a total of 100,000 project staff, stakeholders and benefactors drawn from the 6 (six) counties which are part of Lake Region Economic Bloc (LREB) and will include County Chief Officers, Directors, Departmental Heads, Monitoring and Evaluation Officers, Oversight Committees Members, County Assembly Members, Senior Staff of Departments, Beneficiaries, Boards and Committee Members, Partners, Stakeholders and Members of the Public and Tax Payers.

16.4. Sample and Sample Techniques

The six selected Counties within the Lake Region Economic Bloc (LREB) that participated in the study included Kakamega, Vihiga, Siaya, Kisumu, Homabay, and Migori County Governments who were selected randomly. Researchers such as Mugenda&Mugenda (1999) suggest that one may use a sample size of at least 10 per cent, but for better, more representative results, a higher percentage is better. To obtain sufficient sample, the following model was adopted as described by Yamane (2000)

Sample size calculation $n = \frac{Z^2pq}{d}$

P= Proportion in the target population estimated to have a particular characteristic =0.6

Z=Standard normal deviation set at 1.96 which corresponds with 95% confidence level

q= (1-p) =1-0.6=0.4

d= degree of accuracy desired, set at 0.05

Therefore $n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.6 \times 0.4}{0.05^2} = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.24}{0.0025} = \frac{0.921984}{0.0025} = 397 \sim 398$

0.05² 0.0025 0.0025

Group A: Proportion of respondents involved in M&E = $\frac{398 \times 60}{100} = 239$

100

Group B: Proportion of respondents in projects benefiting from M& E = $\frac{398 \times 40}{100} = 159$

Total sample size= 398

The number was distributed as follows: 66 respondents from each of the six counties totaling to 398 respondents and further distributed as follows, Chief officers- 15, Directors- 30, Departmental Managers -60, Project officers - 120, MCAs -20, County Assembly officers-15, Oversight committees -25, Partners-20, stakeholders-10, beneficiaries - 50, Ward Administrators-15, M&E officers-18. Multi-stage sampling will be utilized; cluster sampling will be used to segregate the population into subpopulation representing the target population. This will form the primary sampling units (PSU). Further sampling was done to identify departments/ministries and sectors from which individuals was investigated drawn.

Purposive sampling techniques was used to identify key informants and respondents knowledgeable in the field of study who constituted the focus group members, this sampling techniques has been suggested by Lwonga (2009) because it involves selection of individuals or objects that yield the most information about the subject under study. Additional secondary data was obtained from reports, publications, journals, policies and legislation.

16.5 Instruments of Data Collection

The study used Likert scale questionnaires to collect data from respondents who were project officers depending on different departments. Interviews were administered to departmental project managers while focused group discussions were administered to officers who carry out projects at county level. It was used to obtain information and to provide an opportunity for the researcher to capture respondent's views on a whole range of issues.

There was three kinds of instruments administered; Likert Scale Questionnaires for the technical team which will include the M&E officers and departmental heads, interviews for Senior officers and Focused Groups Discussion for MCA,s. Likert Scale Questionnaires are useful instruments of collecting primary data since respondents can read and then give responses to each item and they can reach a large number of subjects (Orodho, 2004). Likert Scale Questionnaire use also provides greater anonymity, through questionnaire coding and discrete analysis of the respondent personal details. Statpac (2011) notes that use of questionnaire are less intrusive than telephone interviews or face to face conversations. However, questionnaire format can be limiting in the case of illiterate respondents but again the research assistants were used in clarifying the questions.

16.6 Validity of the Instrument

Validity is the degree to which results obtained from the analysis of data actually represent the phenomena under study, Mugenda and Mugenda (2003). Validity has to be assured both internally and externally. Internal and external validity relates to the overall organization of the research design (Twycross& Shields, 2004). This study recognized the reciprocal balance between the two.

External validity relates to the freedom of generalization provided for in the study. Internal validity on the other hand explained the degree to which the design of study renders itself sufficient in answering the research questions or accepting /nullifying the stated hypothesis. To enhance external validity therefore the study endeavored to draw a representative sample that is randomly selected from the stratified target population of the citizenry in the mentioned counties as outlined in the sampling procedures.

There are three major ways of testing research work validity. These will include Construct validity, Content validity and Criterion validity. Content validity is the extent to which research instrument measure what they are intended to measure (Oso&Onen, 2005). To establish validity, the instruments were given to the supervisors to evaluate the relevance of each item in the instrument to the objectives and rate each item on the scale. Validity was determined using Content Validity Index (C.V.I). This was symbolized as $n^3/4 / N$.

Content validity of the instrument was further ascertained through peer review and scrutiny by research experts, comprising of my supervisor, to ensure that the content in the questionnaire was appropriate and relevant to the study. Supervisor's opinion was sought to check the content and format of the research instrument.

16.7. Reliability of the Instrument

Consistency is very important in Research, Kothari (2004), a measuring instrument is reliable if it provides consistent results. This means that the instrument should give the same results if administered repeatedly. This study used internal consistency technique to ensure reliability. Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) state that in this approach, a score obtained in one item is correlated with scores obtained from other items in the instrument.

This is in agreement with Trochim (2002) that Reliability would refer to the consistency of the measured results over repeated attempts.

Cronbach's coefficient alpha (KR20) was then computed to determine how items correlate among themselves.

The formula is as follows:-

$$KR20 = \frac{k(S^2 - \sum s^2)}{S^2(k - 1)}$$

Where k = Number of items used to measure the concept
 S^2 = Variance of all scores
 s^2 = Variance of individual items

Uma (2006) observes that the closer the reliability coefficient gets to 1.0, the better, and further that in general, reliabilities less than 0.60 are considered to be poor, those in the range of 0.70 acceptable, and those over 0.80 good.

16.8. Methods of Data Analysis

Primary data from the field was edited, coded then responses translated into specific categories. Coding is expected to organize and reduce research data into manageable summaries (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). Quantitative data collected was analyzed, presented and interpreted using both descriptive statistics while thematic analysis techniques was used to analyze qualitative data collected in the open ended questions. Inferential and Descriptive statistics was used to describe the data.

The analyzed data was presented in form of tables. Linear regression analysis was used to establish the relationship and magnitude between Monitoring and evaluation systems process, methods, structures and policies (independent variables) and project performance (dependent variable). The data obtained was also analyzed using SPSS software version 18. Data analysis was also done using multiple regression models since it allows simultaneous investigation of the effect of two or more variables.

The model was to establish the relationship between Monitoring and Evaluation systems process, structures, methods, policies and Performance of projects.

The regression model:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon$$

Where Y = measure the key indicator being Performance of project

β_0 = Constant

β_1 to β_3 = Regression coefficients

X_1 = Systems

X_2 = Methods

X_3 = Structure

X_4 = Policies

ϵ = Coefficient of error

The coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) was used in this analysis to estimate the percentage of variation in the dependent variable that can be explained by the set of independent variables. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistics was used to test the significant of the regression model. Further, in the analysis of variance, the assumption when using student's t -test is that the samples have been drawn from a normally distributed population with equal variances.

The t -test was used to determine the ability of each of the independent variables in explaining the behavior of the dependent variable. Chi-square (χ^2) was used to determine the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

17. Results and Discussions

The data was analyzed, presented and discussed into different sections according to the research questions guiding the study. The overall objective of the study was to assess the effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation systems on the performance of County Governments projects in Lake Region Economic Bloc of Nyanza, Kenya. The principal guiding factors on the analysis presented in this chapter are the specific objectives of the study.

Questionnaires Return / Response Rate

Table: 3. Response Rate

No. of Questionnaires administered	No. of questionnaires filled and returned	Percentage (%)
398	372	93%

Source: Author, (2018)

During the research study, the researcher distributed 398 questionnaires reflecting 100% of the questionnaires in six randomly sampled County Governments. Sixty six (66) questionnaires were distributed in each of the six counties to different levels of monitoring and evaluation or related projects personnel's. 372 (93%) of the questionnaires were returned fully answered while 26 (7%) of the questionnaires were not returned or not properly answered thus not being able to be used for analysis in this research study. This was necessary to establish whether the study was representative or not.

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) 50% response rate is adequate, and a response rate greater than 70% is very good. Hence the response rate of 93% was excellent. This response rate can be attributed to the data collection procedures and research timing and duration, where the researcher pre-notified the potential participants and applied the drop and pick method to allow the respondents ample time to fill the questionnaires, another factor contributing to high questionnaire return rate was that the data collection was conducted during the months of November and December which is a period where most projects are slowed down as employees compile their annual reports before close of the year, these enabled the researcher to find most of the respondents in their offices and not in the field.

Figure .3 Respondents County of Employment

Figure.3. Comparison of Respondents County of Employment and response rate

Source: Author, (2018)

Figure. .3 above shows the distribution of respondents within the six counties of study selected randomly from fourteen counties forming the Lake Region Economic Bloc of Nyanza, Kenya .

Kisumu had 62 (16.7%), Kakamega-63 (16.9%), Vihiga-62 (16.4%), Siaya-60 (16.1%), Homa Bay-62 (16.7%) and Migori-64 (17.2%) questionnaires return rate per county. Majority of counties had more than 91% questionnaire return rate on overall. There were sixty six (66) respondents from each of the six (6) counties and totaling to three hundred and ninety eight (398) respondents for the entire study. The questionnaires were distributed as follows Kisumu-66, Kakamega-66, Vihiga-66, Siaya-66, Homa-bay-66 and Migori-66 project respondents.

Table 4. Respondents age distribution in the County Government Projects

Age Range	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
20 - 29	58	15.7	15.7
30 - 39	106	28.7	44.4
40 - 49	89	24.1	68.6
50 - 59	91	24.7	93.2
60+	25	6.8	
Not stated	3		
Total	372	100.0	100.0

Source: Author, (2018)

In the table 4.3.1 above, 106 of the respondents are in the age bracket of 30-39 constituting 28.7% of total respondents. Followed by 91 respondent in age bracket of 50-59 which constitute (24.7%). The age bracket of 40-49 were 89 respondent at (24.1%) while 58 respondents (15.7%) were in the age range of 20-29. Only 25 respondents were aged 60 years and above at (6.8%). As can be observed from the table 4.3.1 above, majority of County Governments staff are in the age brackets of 30- 39 and 50-59 years of age accounting for 53.4%.

During the focus group discussion, respondents alluded that the majority in the age bracket of 30-39 (28.7%) while those in the age bracket of 50-59 (24.7%) are those who were transferred or absorbed from former local governments ministries and national governments agencies that were devolved. The staff in the age of 60 and above (6.8%) are mostly Service Delivery Units (SDU,s), Governance units, Protocol units among others.

Figure: 4 Gender Distribution of Respondents in County Government M&E of Projects

Source: Author, (2018)

Figure 4. above, male were 227 accounting for (61%) and female were 145 constituting (39%) of the respondents. The researcher sought to know the gender distribution on the County Governments projects. This question was important to the researcher to ascertain whether the County Public Service Boards applied or observed the gender rule in employment of County Staff. The majority of County Governments projects were male dominated with fewer women mostly carrying out special projects assignments.

The researcher sought to establish why the projects were male dominance, the reasons are that females preferred office work as opposed to project field work, other reasons advanced during focus group discussion are that male were more aggressive than females in job hunting and able to do any job offered to them than females who sometimes selected the type of job. It was also established that majority of females working in the projects were aged between 20-39 years and had worked for less than 6 years.

Figure 5 Distribution of respondent's age against education level in the County Government Projects

Source: Author, (2018)

In Figure 5 above, on the level of education, degree holders were leading with 132 respondents being undergraduate and above accounting for (36.6%) of respondents, the diploma holders were 130 respondents being (36%) of total respondents. A level certificate holders were 40 (11.1%), O-level certificate 52 (14.4%) and Primary certificate holders 7 respondents translating to (1.9%).

During the focus group discussions, the researcher sought to find out why there is almost equal or small difference in the number of degree holders and diploma holders in the County Governments projects. The researcher found majority of former local government staff who were absorbed in counties went back to colleges and universities to either pursue a degree or a diploma course in order to improve their skills or to get promotion, move from one department to another or to avoid being rendered redundant in the projects work.

Figure 6. County Government methods for conducting M&E are clear for each project

Source: Author, (2018)

Figure (6) above, 254 (63%) of respondents disagree that the County Government methods for conducting M&E for projects are clear, 52(14%) of respondents strongly disagreed while only 35(9%) agreed that there is some clarity on the methods for conducting M&E in the County Government Projects. 31 (8%) of respondents were not able to decide whether or not the method is clear. In general, the perception is that majority feels the method for conducting monitoring and evaluation of County Government Projects are unclear.

From the focus group discussions, respondents noted that a part from few projects like health department where they conduct monitoring and evaluation purposely for (HIS), the methods used for other projects or departments are unclear, and in most cases, vary from department to department and projects to projects and hence unclear. They went further

to state that even parameters and tools for M&E data collection is not designed for projects. They noted that what officers do is basically field visits in the name of M&E. Its therefore difficult to say that there is an existing method for monitoring and evaluation of County Government Projects.

Scriven(1967), concurs that there is increased need and interest in M&E methods among the development communities due to a stronger focus on the results produced and the means to produce them through interventions. M&E methods allow those involved to assess the impact of a particular activity, to determine how it could be done better using different methods and to show what action is being taken by different stakeholders.

Jimenez and Patrinos (2008), suggest that , M&E method should be clear, among other methods government institutions and organizations could choose depending on the projects includes; Participatory Approach method of Monitoring and Evaluation which allows project stakeholders to be actively involved in decision-making and generates a sense of ownership of M&E results and recommendations, and build local capacity. The Cost-benefit and cost-effectiveness analysis Method is a cost benefit analysis tools used to assess whether the cost of an activity is justified by its impact. Cost-benefit measures inputs and outputs in monetary terms, whereas cost-effectiveness looks at outputs in non-monetary terms, Public Expenditure Tracking Surveys method (PETS) are surveys that measure the amount of funds received at each point in the chain of public service delivery, from the treasury to the project, e.g classroom or health clinic where the funds are intended to be spent (Zaltsman, 2006). It's a method that traces (monitors) the flow of public funds and assesses whether resources reach the intended recipients. They help diagnose service delivery problems and improve accountability.

Figure .7 M&E methods focuses on learning process

Source: *Author,(2018)*

Figure 7.above, significant representation of 51% (188) respondents feels that the County Government M&E method does not focus on learning process. 29% (108) respondents also strongly disagreed with the statements that the method focuses on monitoring, evaluation, learning and accountability. 13%(49) respondents had no opinion as to whether the methods focus on learning process and only 7% (27) agrees with the sentiments that the method of M&E also focuses on learning process. From the analysis above, it can be concluded that the County Government monitoring and evaluation method does not focus on learning and accountability process.

Further, during the focus group discussions, the respondents affirmed that there is no specified monitoring and evaluation method in County Government Projects. For the few departments that has M&E units, the methods are selected by the same departments and vary from time to time and project to project. As to whether the methods focuses on learning and accountability, the respondents had a feeling that it does not, since the method is not structured in line with the objectives of the projects. The purpose of monitoring, evaluation and learning practices is to apply knowledge gained from evidence and analysis to improve development outcomes and ensure accountability for the resources used to achieve them.

Willard (2008), affirms that, when investing in monitoring and evaluation method, institutions implementing projects realize the return on this investment by tying it to learning priorities. Learning from M&E method means using M&E data and information as evidence for accountability and informing decision-making for management and governance purposes, course adjustments, and future designs.eg, monitoring data are used to track the progress of a mechanism in achieving set objectives. Evaluation is used to determine how and why results are being achieved, or not, as well as discovering unintended, unexpected, or emerging results.

It is therefore important to remember that monitoring, evaluation are not the end goal, but rather the means by which projects achieve the outcomes more effectively based on the method used. The knowledge generating through monitoring or evaluation is and method is used in contributing to real-time decision-making about design and implementation, institutions need to take a deeper look at their M&E method (Campo,2005). Institutions can also assess other aspects such whether the method is enabling conditions and decision-making process and the effective use of analysis of monitoring data and evaluations.

Figure 8. County M&E method allows stakeholders and beneficiaries participation and feedback on the projects.
Source: *Author (2018)*

Figure 8 above, 165 (44%) of the respondents alluded that the M&E method of County Governments projects has no framework or do not allow for stakeholders and beneficiaries participation in monitoring and evaluation of projects. A further 49 (13%) strongly disagreed again bringing the total number of respondents who disagreed to 214 (57%) while 104 (28%) Agreed that the method allows for stakeholders and beneficiaries participation or involvement in the process. A further 54 (16%) of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed on whether the method allows for stakeholders and beneficiaries involvement in M&E of projects. In general, a large number of respondents says that the M&E method of County Government Projects does not allow for full stakeholders and beneficiaries participation on monitoring and evaluation of projects.

Maina, (2013) states that, stakeholders are individuals, groups or organizations that have a specific interest or will be affected in some significant way by the outcome of the evaluation process or that are affected by the performance of the intervention, or both. Most interventions have a wide range of stakeholders, some more influential than others, either because they benefit from the project, they fund some of its activities, or have political interests. Not all stakeholders have the same stake in the interventions and it is important to recognize the level of influence each stakeholder has on the project and its monitoring and evaluation.

Oakley (2013), confirms that there are dangers inherent in not making an inventory of the stakeholders and involving them in monitoring and evaluation of projects or in the intervention being evaluated and in the evaluation itself. Normally, those who have an interest in the success or failure of the project also have an interest in how the evaluation is carried out, its findings, and how these findings affect the future of the project. The stakeholders have been described as a powerful means of understanding and influencing the organizations systems, structures methods and approaches in the project deliveries.

Oakley (2013), further says that, the involvement of stakeholders and beneficiaries in monitoring and evaluation of projects is intended to broaden the governance and management's vision of its roles and responsibilities beyond the, results, impact and profit maximization function. Stakeholders are identified in the input output models of the project, this also include interests and claims of all stockholding groups (Maina, 2013).

Mulwa and Nguluu (2007) further elaborated that the stakeholder entails all persons or groups with legitimate interests participating in a project for its success and do so to obtain benefits and that there is no preset priority of one set of interests and benefits over another

Involvement of stakeholders in M&E increases the sense of national and local ownership of project activities and ultimately promotes the likelihood that the project activities and their impact would be sustainable.

Lin-Lin, Yang, Hu and Chan (2014), agree that the influence, role and treatment of stakeholders is related to the long term survival of the project and the success of the projects can be influenced greatly by the participation of various stakeholders.

An Assessment of the Effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation Methods on the Performance of.

The stakeholders interact and relate to execute the project with the aim of achieving set standards and thus have a common interest of project success. In this instance, the stakeholders play a very important role in the development of project systems, structures and approaches for successful delivery of project results. Furthermore, in County Government Projects, politicians have a key role in the identification as well as implementation of the projects and their choices as regards the methods influenced by political maximization (Campo,2005: GoK, 2012).

Figure:9 M&E Methods of County Government Projects facilitate achievement of desired results and objectivesSource: (Survey Data, 2018)

Figure (9)above shows the perception of the respondents on the statement on whether the M&E methods of County Governments projects facilitate the achievements of desired results and objectives. 177 (48%) of the respondents disagree while 29(8%) of respondents strongly disagreed. 111(30%) of the respondents could not either agree or disagree, 48(13%) of respondents agreed and 7(2%) also strongly agreed. A total of 208 respondents (56%) disagree while only a paltry 55(14%) agreed. Therefore it can be concluded that the County Government monitoring and evaluation method does not facilitate the achievement of desired results and objectives.

During the focus group discussion, the respondents noted that most of the County Governments projects have no M&E plan. The projects are not being evaluated in order to compare the planned verses the achieved results but rather projects are implemented as a daily routine activity. It was also noted that there is no clear and agreed monitoring and evaluation method for county projects that can be used as a bench mark to measure with results and objectives. Methods of monitoring and evaluation differ from project to project and department to department but most importantly do not exist. This has hampered the achievement of projects objectives in most projects.

Choosing the method and approaches of project monitoring and evaluation is an area of growing importance for the development community (Zaltsman, 2006). It allows those involved in development activities to choose wisely and to learn from experience, to achieve better results and to be more accountable. There is increased interest in M&E methods that is able to transform the project and ensure high project success and impact among the development communities due to a stronger focus on the results produced and the means to produce them through interventions. M&E methods and processes allow those involved to assess the impact of a particular activity, to determine how it could be done better using different methods and approaches and to show what action is being taken by different stakeholders (Scriven,1967) . This should translate into a more effective and transparent way of working. There are different methods that can be employed by the projects but more importantly, the method of monitoring and evaluation should be chosen keenly to ensure the achievement of desired results, while meeting the project objectives. Each M&E method will produce different results. The organization should therefore ensure that each project choose the right M&E method that will facilitate the achievement of the planned results and give greater impact.

Figure 10. County Government Projects M&E method are anchored on M&E project policy.

Source: *Survey Data (2018)*

In the above figure (10), 39% (145) respondents disagree with the statement, 33%(124) strongly disagree, 16%(59) respondents were undecided, while 9%(34) and 3%(10) agreed respectively. From the analysis above it can be observed that majority of the respondents 72% disagree with the statement that the M&E method is anchored on the policy. while only 12% of the respondents agreed with the statement. From the respondents view, it can be concluded that the M&E methods of County Government Projects are not anchored or supported by policy procedures.

On focus group discussion, the respondents also affirmed that the County Government Projects monitoring and evaluation method is not supported by any policy. Currently there is no county policy or legislation supporting the M&E activities of the county. However, some projects have a guideline on the field visit which is one of the M&E methods in the County Governments.

The respondents further observed that having a clear Method which is anchored on the policy and legislation could facilitate effective method of conducting monitoring and evaluation projects of County Government, The policy could contain the procedure method on conducting monitoring and evaluation to avoid the feeling of that some evaluators may use the method as a witch-hunt.

Blakemore, (1998), suggest that policies and procedures are designed to influence and determine all major decisions and actions, and all activities take place within the boundaries set by them. Procedures are the specific methods employed to express policies in action in day-to-day operations of the organization. Together, policies and procedures ensure that a point of view held by the governing or management body of an organization is translated into steps that result in an outcome and results. It's therefore necessary that the procedure method for conducting M&E of projects be outlined in the project policy documents and generally the organizational operational policy document.

Paquette (2002) agrees that project monitoring and evaluation method is important as it is a guiding principle used to set project direction on the methodology and procedures for performing project monitoring and evaluation. It can be a course of action to guide and influence M&E decisions. It should be used as a guide to decision making under a given set of circumstances within the framework of objectives, goals and management philosophies as determined by governing body or management (Spizer, 1987).

Stone & Diane, (2008) asserted that, the principles and policies provide the basis for monitoring and evaluation data controls method, criteria and guidance for monitoring and evaluation process decision making and direction and guidance to ensure M&E data collection and analysis, procedures, and records are uniform throughout the projects, departments and ministries.

18. Regression Analysis

	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	β	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig
Constant	11.126	0.234		2.212	0.021
M and E systems	0.825	0.293	0.027	2.123	0.014
M and E structure	0.652	0.268	0.054	1.496	0.047
M and E methods	0.516	0.241	0.067	1.155	0.021
M and E policies	0.764	0.278	0.073	1.389	0.053

Table 5: Multiple Regression Equation

Regression analysis was utilized to investigate the relationship between the variables. These included an error term, where the dependent variable was expressed with a combination of independent variables.

The unknown parameters in the model were estimated, using observed values of the dependent and independent variables.

The following model represents the regression equation representing the relationship between effectiveness of M&E methods as a linear function of the independent variables (M&E methods, M&E systems, M&E structures, M&E and M&E policies), with ϵ representing the error term. The regression model was therefore used to describe how the mean of the dependent variable changes with the changing conditions.

(Equation 1: Regression Equation)

Where; Y_1 = measure the key indicator being Performance of projects (Success, Results, Impacts)

$$Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots \text{When } \beta_5 = 0 \dots\dots \text{(Equation 1)}$$

β_0 = Constant

X_1 = Monitoring and evaluation methods

X_2 = Monitoring and Evaluation systems process

X_3 = Monitoring and evaluation structures

X_4 = Monitoring and evaluation policies

ϵ = representing the error term

The coefficient was obtained as follow

Table: 6 Multiple Regression Analysis

	Un-standardized coefficients		Standardized Co-efficient		
	β	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
Constant	11.126	0.234		2.212	0.021
M & E methods	0.825	0.0293	0.027	2.123	0.014
M&E systems P	0.652	0.268	0.054	1.496	0.047
M&E structure	0.516	0.241	0.067	1.155	0.021
M&E policies	0.764	0.278	0.073	1.389	0.053

When the Beta (β) values above are incorporated into the equation 1 above.

$$Y_1 = 11.126 + 0.825 X_1 + 0.652 X_2 + 0.516 X_3 + 0.764 X_4 + \epsilon \dots\dots \text{Equation 2.}$$

(Equation 2: Regression Equation with Beta Values)

Referring to the above regression equation, when all factors are taken into account, effectiveness of M&E methods is equal to 11.126. The Standardized Beta Coefficients give a measure of the contribution of each variable to the model. In this case, a large value indicates that a unit change in this predictor variable has a large effect on the criterion variable. The t and Sig (p) values give an indication of the impact or contribution of each predictor variable, a big absolute t value and small p-value suggests that a predictor variable is having a large impact on the criterion variable. At 5% level of significance and 95% level of confidence. The Monitoring and Evaluation methods had a 0.825 level of significance, Monitoring and Evaluation systems had a 0.652 level of significance, Monitoring and Evaluation structure had a 0.516 level of significance and Monitoring and Evaluation policies had a 0.764 level of significance.

6. Regression Model.

Table 7 Regression Model (Summary)

Table 7. Regression of the Coefficient of Effectiveness of Monitoring and Evaluation Methods

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std Error of Estimate	Change (statistics)				
					R ² Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	0.888 ^a	0.896	0.887	0.44738	0.964	109.403	4	9	0.000

Source: Author, (2018)

Predictors: (Constant), M&E methods, M&E systems procedures, M&E structure and M&E policies.

The above variables, collectively, show that 87.7% of variation or change in the effectiveness of M&E systems is explained by the variables considered in the model, being M&E systems procedures, M&E structure, M&E methods and M&E policies indicated by the coefficient of effectiveness (R²) which is also evidenced by F change 109.403 > p-values (0.05). This implies that these variables are significant (since the p values < 0.05) and therefore should be considered as part of effectiveness of M&E methods on the performance of County Governments projects. This study therefore identifies monitoring and evaluation method, monitoring and evaluation systems process, monitoring and evaluation structure, and monitoring and evaluation policies as effective M&E on the performance of County Government Projects.

19. Correlation Coefficient

To measure the correlation, Pearson was used to measure the degree of association between variables. Pearson correlation coefficients range from -1 to +1. Negative values indicates negative correlation and positive values indicates positive correlation where Pearson coefficient indicates weak correlation, Pearson coefficient > 0.3 < 0.5 indicates moderate correlation and Pearson coefficient > 0.5 indicates strong correlation.

Table 8. Correlation Coefficient

	M&E Methods	M&E Systems	M&E structures	M&E policies	Effectiveness of M&E
M&E Methods	1				
M&E structure	0.624	1			
M&E systems procedure	0.601	0.598	1		
M&E policies	0.628	0.611	0.543	1	
Effectiveness of M&E	0.771	0.634	0.542	0.769	1

Source: Author (2018)

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1- tailed)

The analysis above shows monitoring and evaluation systems procedures has the strongest positive (Pearson correlation coefficient = 0.771) influence on effective M&E methods. In addition, M&E policies, M&E structures and M&E system process are positively correlated to effectiveness of M&E (Pearson correlation coefficient = 0.769, 0.634 and 0.542) respectively.

The correlation matrix implies that the independent variables: being M&E methods, M&E systems procedures M&E structure and M&E policies are crucial on the effectiveness of M&E on the performance of the projects as shown by their strong and positive relationship with the dependent variables.

Conclusion

The Citizens are increasingly demanding and calling upon county governments to demonstrate results and impacts of the projects they undertake, besides demands for greater accountability and transparency, citizens, stakeholders and beneficiaries are also demanding greater efficiency and effectiveness of monitoring and evaluation methods for projects. This is to ensure better projects results.

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The effectiveness of M&E methods on the performance of projects is determined by various factors and approaches including framework approach, rapid appraisal, participatory, cost-effectiveness, impact and public expenditure tracking methods among others.

Recommendation

The County Government should develop results management framework method (RMF) as a strategic approach to be applied in all aspects of the project monitoring and evaluation process. Embracing Results-based monitoring and evaluation method will place particular emphasis on outcomes and impact. The County Government project monitoring and evaluation method should also be able to determine, and show evidence that, planned outcomes are actualized and has a worthwhile contribution to the national goals including the Kenyan Big Four Agenda (B₄) agenda and Vision 2030. Furthermore, the County Government projects should develop appropriate monitoring and evaluation systems for different projects while embracing both qualitative and quantitative approaches and methodologies.

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